

RISE OF ISLAMIC FINTECH IN CENTRAL ASIA

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Annotation: *Fintech, or financial technology, is changing how people can manage their finances. In the UK, the impact of financial technology has been profound. Within five years, the emergence of challenger banks and revolutionary new products challenged the traditional monopoly of banks in the financial system. In short, technology is empowering society by democratizing the banking system. It is important to note that the influence of fintech is not limited to established markets. If we look at developing regions such as Central Asia, a new generation of innovative fintech breakthroughs are applying advanced technological solutions to achieve broader development goals. This is not a continuous application of existing technologies. Instead, creative thinkers who understand the main challenges facing people in countries such as Tajikistan and Uzbekistan are promoting the digital transformation of the region. If current trends continue, Central Asia will become a new center of fintech innovation. The essence of the region's success lies not only in the reproduction of consumer financial and investment products that are currently offered in places such as London, New York and San Francisco, but also in the creation of new fintech products and services. The core of this new wave of innovation is the growth of Islamic financial technologies. When we talk about Islamic finance, we mean a banking system that adheres to the principles of Sharia. These principles include a ban on profiting from debt, paying interest, and investing capital in restricted sectors such as alcohol, tobacco, and gambling. It also provides financial and social stability by encouraging asset-backed financing. Obviously, interest payments are inherent in the functioning of non-Islamic banking systems. In response, Islamic challenger banks around the world offer Muslims the opportunity to access Sharia-compliant systems.*

Practically, Islamic fintech has become the fastest growing segment of financial technologies among the countries of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC). It is estimated that the share of Islamic financial technologies in the OIC countries accounted for 49 billion US dollars in transactions in 2020. Although this is an impressive figure, its true potential is revealed when compared with global financial technology transactions — Islamic financial technologies accounted for only 0.7% of global fintech transactions last year. The Global Islamic Fintech Report predicts that the volume of transactions in the Islamic financial technology sector of the OIC countries will grow at a cumulative annual growth rate of 21%, or \$ 128 billion. This compares with the 15 percent growth

expected for conventional fintech companies over the same time period. Given that Central Asian countries such as Tajikistan and Uzbekistan are part of the OIC, it is obvious that this region is the best for growth. Understanding the needs of the Muslim population, innovative companies use existing fintech solutions that already exist for consumer finance and retail investments, modifying these products and services to comply with Sharia law. This not only meets the needs of people of the Islamic faith; it also supports the creation of an alternative financial system that is sustainable and promotes broader economic development in regions such as Central Asia. Leaving aside the positive developments, there are still problems that need to be solved if Islamic finance in Central Asia wants to fully realize its potential. It is estimated that half of the region's population is still not covered by financial services. A 2019 study showed that only 79% of residents of Kazakhstan and about 50% of residents of Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan had access to the Internet. Although these numbers have probably improved in subsequent years, the fact remains that fintech's success is limited if a significant number of people do not have access to the Internet. While the world is becoming globalized, different cultures still manage their finances differently. There is no universal solution, and, as discussed above, new innovations should be inclusive, not exclusive. Fortunately, a new generation of fintech companies is using technology to meet the needs of the population who did not have access to fintech solutions.

Key words: *Islamic Fintech, fintech innovation, Islamic banking, Islamic finance, principles of Sharia, Islamic Banking, Islamic financial technologies, fintech solutions, Fintech Report, new innovations.*

Central Asia is rapidly becoming the global capital of fintech innovation, especially when it comes to Islamic finance. To maintain momentum, government support, education, and infrastructure investments are needed to expand the digital capabilities of the population. For example, Uzbek fintech companies expand cooperation on Islamic finance. Fido-Biznes together with Kuwait's ITS Group will create integrated solutions for the implementation of various Islamic window products in banks in Uzbekistan.

As a result of the negotiations, the parties came to a mutual understanding of goals and objectives and signed a memorandum of cooperation and interaction reflecting the intentions of both sides in the development of Islamic finance in Uzbekistan. The main integrated products of ITS Group based on the ETHIX NG line with the Fido-Biznes product "Integrated Automated Banking System" (IABS) of the seventh version are identified. There is a clear trend in the development of financial services in Uzbekistan that in the near future the Islamic window will become an alternative type of traditional financial services provided by banks to the population and business. Since the vast majority of the population of Uzbekistan is Muslim, reforms in the banking sector focused on the introduction of Islamic finance will predictably lead to the creation of a favorable economic environment for the population and business, will contribute to the expansion of banking services and the

stabilization of prices for them. Another start-up is IMAN. IMAN became the first startup from Uzbekistan to reach the finals of the largest international Seedstars competition. The founder and CEO of the company, Rustam Rakhmatov, told Kapital.uz about the business model of the Islamic financial platform and plans to transfer capital from developed countries to developing countries. Fintech startup IMAN raised \$1 million during the next investment round. This was reported by the company's press service. The startup received funds from 6 venture investors and funds from Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, the USA and Singapore. Among them are Tesla Capital, Battery Road Digital Holdings, Le Mercier's Capital, Vector Crypto Capital. The funds were also allocated by UZCARD Ventures and IT Park. With the money raised, IMAN is going to create a super-application in the field of Islamic finance. Initially, it will be launched in Uzbekistan, and from 2023 — in neighboring countries with a predominantly Muslim population. Investments will help to scale technologies and simplify integration with retail outlets in Uzbekistan, IMAN CEO Rustam Rakhmatov added. This way the company will be able to develop partnerships with merchants in all sectors. Now investors are attracted to emerging markets with high growth rates, mainly young populations and favorable policies — such as Uzbekistan. In addition, there is a growing demand for investment opportunities that meet the norms of Islam.

"This gives IMAN the opportunity to create a digital bridge between investors in developed markets and consumers in emerging markets with a Muslim majority," said Mark Zubov, IMAN's CFO. Now the team is planning to enter neighboring countries — with a young Muslim population, developed e-commerce and digital payments. For Battery Road, an investment fund from Singapore and New York, the investment in IMAN was the first in Central Asia. The fast-growing economy combined with the convenience of using technology opens up opportunities for Islamic fintech, the fund noted. Earlier, Spot reported that Alif, a fintech startup operating in Uzbekistan since 2019, has attracted \$8 million in investments. Spot also wrote that Jobster had raised \$150,000 from Mohirdev. IMAN combines three products: marketplace, installment service and investment. All services work according to the principles of Islamic finance. In 2021, he became the first startup from Uzbekistan in the Seedstars world finals, although he could not win.

Another example could be Tayyab. The first digital Islamic card Tayyab has been launched in Kazakhstan. Among the advantages of the first digital Islamic Tayyab card are full compliance with Sharia law, instant free issue, free maintenance, contactless payments via Apple pay and Samsung pay without commissions. The first digital Islamic card Tayyab has been launched in Kazakhstan. Compliance with the principles of Islamic finance is confirmed by the international Sharia Council Shariah Review Bureau (Saudi Arabia), as well as the Spiritual Administration of Muslims of Kazakhstan. Customer card balances are not used to generate interest income, and no interest is accrued on them. You can issue a card in a minute by installing the Tayyab

mobile app in the Apple Store or Play Market. You can immediately make instant transfers and contactless payments around the world using Apple Pay and Samsung Pay wallets. If necessary, you can order a plastic VISA card with delivery. You can store money in four currencies: Kazakhstani tenge, US dollar, euro, Russian ruble. You can withdraw cash at any ATM in the world. The card was launched by the first Kazakh Islamic fintech Tayyab in partnership with Bank RBK and VISA payment system. One of Tayyab's institutional investors is the Dubai Fintech Ventures venture fund.

"In addition to the convenience of using financial functions that correspond to the latest global trends. We provide our users with a convenient service for practicing the Islamic lifestyle. For example, only in the Tayyab application you can easily find the mosque, namazkhana or halal cafe nearest to you. Also available in the application are namaz and azan times, Qibla compass, dhikr counter, zakat calculator and much more," said Daniyar Uspanov, CEO of Tayyab. Additional features of the first digital Islamic Tayyab card is that it is not intended for payment in casinos, as well as in any gambling and lottery establishments, specialized stores selling alcohol and tobacco products, while the restriction does not apply to department stores selling products. The card is not intended to pay for goods and services of bars and nightclubs, while the restriction does not apply to restaurants and cafes.

"We are starting with the most important, every day necessary services for everyone, for example, payments, transfers and personal finance management, as well as with the functions of supporting daily religious practice. Next, we will increase the number of services, services and partners, but they will all comply with the principles of simple & halal, that is, "simple and halal," says Daniyar Uspanov.

The Tayyab project began as a successful startup that entered the top ten of the accelerator in Dubai. Already at this stage, the service was able to attract the attention of the leading players in the United Arab Emirates market. As it turned out later, Tayyab was needed both in Kazakhstan and abroad, which in the future opens the project to the Middle East. Having studied the market, the authors of the service realized that most of the Muslim world uses outdated Islamic financial services, and the world is experiencing an urgent need to offer digital Islamic banking.

"There is no analogue of Tayyab in the world, and therefore we count on the serious support of the progressive Muslim community. The beginning of this has already been laid. Having successfully completed the acceleration, we immediately received shareholders in the form of the Dubai Fintech Ventures venture fund, whose partners were the VISA payment system, the Dubai International Financial Center DIFC, HSBC and one of the largest banks in the UAE – Mashreq bank. Bank RBK has become our partner in Kazakhstan, and the strategic software development partner is one of the leaders of the IT industry in Kazakhstan - the Prime Source group of companies. The Sharia compliance partner is the Shariah Review Bureau International Sharia Council from Saudi Arabia," adds Ivan Kamensky.

What does Tayyab offer its users? The project is actively launching with digital debit Islamic cards, also providing users with the opportunity to make instant money transfers, pay for goods and services without commissions, make free withdrawals within the established limits at any ATM in the world, use contactless payment technologies such as Samsung Pay, Apple Pay and much more. Daily digital services of a religious nature are also available in the application, including digital services of Sadaqa and Zakat, prayer schedule, azan notifications, Qibla compass, Tasbih counter and even halal maps to search for a mosque or namazkhana, a point of sale of halal food or an ATM nearby. Any service options – from ordering cards to any transactions – work in one touch online, you can become a customer through a mobile application through digital onboarding.

In general, according to the founders of the project, Tayyab's mission is to simplify Islamic finance as much as possible without cutting their capabilities. This is an integral quality of all services provided by the service. Thus, the framework of Islamic law restricts Muslims in performing certain financial transactions. The Tayyab financial service fully complies with all the norms and principles of Sharia – there are no riba (operations related to usury) and hidden commissions in it. According to the basic principles of Islamic finance, money and debt are only a means of exchange and cannot be an object of trade, and transactions must be secured with real assets. Therefore, the founders of Tayyab do not earn on deposits and loans, as in a regular bank – that is, they do not work with those products on which interest is accrued, and the risks of any transaction must be shared by at least two parties.

The service takes into account the following points: the remaining money on Tayyab cards is not used by the company to receive interest income; no interest is accrued on the remaining money on the cards; the card is not intended for payment in casinos, as well as in any gambling and lottery business establishments; the card is not intended for payment in specialized stores selling alcohol and tobacco products, at the same time, the restriction does not apply to department stores selling groceries; the card is not intended to pay for goods and services of bars and nightclubs, while the restriction does not apply to restaurants and cafes.

"Thanks to projects such as Tayyab, the ecosystem of Islamic finance in Kazakhstan acquires new sides. It is important that we will be able to positively influence the popularization of an ethical lifestyle and the formation of moral values of every Muslim. In addition, Islamic financial services will meet the service needs of those people who, for religious reasons, are not ready to use traditional banking products," says Daniyar Uspanov.

The owners of Tayyab note that there are many different Islamic financial services offered by Islamic banks in the world, but there is not a single solution among them in the field of providing digital Islamic financial services. That is why the uniqueness of Tayyab products is based on simplicity, reliability and ease of use.

Today, the Tayyab service has already been fully tested and is ready to work. Instagram and Facebook can download the tayyab app in the App Store and Playmarket, and learn more about the principles of its work and the philosophy of creation on the project website or on the social networks Instagram and Facebook. In the near future, the Tayyab team will begin onboarding clients in Kazakhstan.

It should be noted that at the moment the Islamic finance market is represented by about 700 institutions operating in more than 90 countries of the world. The volume of the segment is about \$2.4 trillion, by 2023 it is projected to grow to \$3.8 trillion. The largest sector of Islamic finance is Islamic banking, which forms 72.4% of the market. At the same time, the demand for Islamic banking services is similarly growing. Thus, by December 2020, the loan portfolio of Islamic banks increased by 47.4% compared to the same period a year earlier and amounted to 39.7 billion tenge. In Kazakhstan, the average annual increase in assets of Muslim banks over the past three years is 30.3%. Given the growing interest of Kazakhstan in this market segment, our country is close to the leadership among the CIS countries in the development of Islamic finance in general.

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